

**PROFESSOR SAMIKHAN ASHIRBOYEV SCIENTIFIC AND
PEDAGOGICAL SCHOOL: PEDAGOGICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL
ACTIVITY AND EXPERIENCE IN TRAINING SCIENTIFIC PERSONNEL**

Yuldoshev Umidjon Yuldoshevich

Professor of the International Nordic University, PhD.

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-8799-6169>

yumid090@gmail.com

Abstract: This article analyzes the scientific and pedagogical activities of Samikhan Ashirbayev, his pedagogical and methodological views, and the areas of activity that have formed as a scientific school. The professor's experience in educational theory, language teaching methodology, and training of scientific personnel, as well as his role as a scientific supervisor, are highlighted. The article analyzes the scientist's scientific approach based on the integration of philology and pedagogy, its importance in the modern education system, and the prospects of his scientific school on a scientific and theoretical basis.

Keywords: Scientific school, pedagogical activity, methodological approach, scientific leadership, language teaching methodology, philology, pedagogy, training of scientific personnel, educational theory.

In today's process of globalization and informatization, the education system is tasked with training highly qualified specialists with modern knowledge and competencies. In such circumstances, the role and importance of scientific and pedagogical schools are increasing. In particular, scientific schools of eminent scientists play an important role in ensuring the integration of science and education, directing young researchers to scientific activities, and systematizing pedagogical experiences.

One of the scientists who has been working effectively in the fields of Uzbek philology and pedagogy is Samixon Ashirboyev. He is a doctor of philological sciences, a professor who has achieved significant scientific results not only in linguistics and literary studies, but also in pedagogy, educational methodology, and the system of training scientific personnel. Professor Samikhan Ashirbayev, who

currently works as the head of the department at the Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi, has managed to form a large scientific and pedagogical school around him. This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the professor's scientific and pedagogical activities, methodological views, experience in scientific leadership, and the factors that contributed to the formation of his scientific school.

Although Professor Samixon Ashirboyev's scientific work initially focused on philology, his research later became closely intertwined with pedagogical methodology, educational technologies, and language teaching methods. This situation indicates the strong interdisciplinary integration in the scientist's scientific views.

The following areas are of priority importance in the scientist's scientific work:

- methodology of teaching native language and literature;
- innovative approaches to language teaching;
- development of pedagogical competencies;
- theory of education and upbringing;
- research methodology;
- system of training scientific personnel.

The pedagogical views of the professor are based on the humanitarian principles of Education. He pays special attention to the formation of a student as a person in the educational process. According to the scientist, a modern teacher should not only be a knowledge provider, but also a spiritual educator and scientific guide.

The combination of theory and practice is the main principle in the pedagogical work of Professor Samikhan Ashirbayev. He places particular emphasis on interactive methods, analytical thinking, independent research, and the development of scientific reasoning skills in teaching methodology.

The methodological views of my teacher Samixon Ashirboyev are formed in harmony with the modern educational paradigm. The professor emphasizes that the student or student should be at the center of education. Such an approach takes into account the individual ability, need and interest of each learner. As a result, the effectiveness of education increases, and an independent thinking person is formed. [1].

The scientist considers the integration of philology and pedagogy as one of

the main directions of his scientific work. He argues that the methodology of language teaching should include not only linguistic knowledge, but also psychological, didactic and communicative competencies.

The use of modern pedagogical technologies plays an important role in the professor's scientific work. In particular:

- interactive methods;
- problem-based learning;
- project-based learning;
- competence-based approach;
- elements of digital pedagogy.

These approaches serve to improve the quality of Education.

Professor Samikhon Ashirboyev defines the formation of scientific thinking as a priority in his pedagogical activity. Orienting students to scientific research, developing skills in writing scientific articles, and teaching research methodology are important aspects of a scientist's work.

A Scientific School is a system of scientific views, methodological approaches and scientific traditions formed around a particular scientific leader. The scientific and Pedagogical School, formed by Professor Samikhon Ashirboyev, brings together many researchers who today work in various specialties.

The main features of this scientific school are: interdisciplinary integration; the combination of scientific research and pedagogical practice; openness to methodological innovations; support for young scientists; and the formation of a culture of scientific communication. Among the professor's students are researchers engaged in scientific activities in the fields of pedagogy, language teaching methodology, philology, literary studies, and other areas. This indicates that the scientist's scientific school is multidisciplinary and steadily developing. [2.].

As a scientific supervisor, the professor instills in his students skills such as independent scientific thinking, identifying a scientific problem, choosing research methods, drawing scientific conclusions, and adhering to the principles of academic honesty.

One of the most important aspects of the scientific activity of Professor Samikhon Ashirboyev is his effective activity in training scientific personnel. Under the direction of the scientist, many master's theses, doctor of Philosophy (PhD) and Doctor of science (DSc) theses have been defended. Identifying and developing the scientific potential of each researcher is a priority of the professor's work. He helps

to determine the direction of research based on the student's interests and scientific potential. [5].

The professor considers systematicity and responsibility in scientific activity to be important factors. Students are required to adhere to scientific ethics, master the culture of working with sources, and thoroughly master the methodological foundations of research. A special place in the activity of the Professor is occupied by the teacher-disciple principle, which is characteristic of national scientific schools. This tradition ensures not only scientific knowledge, but also the continuity of pedagogical culture and human qualities.

The professor strives to bring his students into the international scientific arena. Participation in international conferences, scientific journals, and academic cooperation projects is considered an important part of the activities of young researchers.

Professor Samikhan Ashirboyev is one of the scientists who has also conducted effective scientific work in the field of language teaching methodology. He pays special attention to the issues of communicative approach; competence-based education; development of speech activity; text-based technologies; and the formation of creative thinking in mother tongue education.. [3].

The scientific and Pedagogical School of Professor Samikhon Ashirboyev has been providing effective results not only in philology and pedagogy, but also in the direction of music education. In the scientific environment formed on the basis of the leadership and methodological views of the scientist, research on music pedagogy is also developing. In particular, research on the competence-based approach in education, the development of creative thinking, and the use of interactive methods is also reflected in the methodology of music education.

Some of the students who formed the professor's scientific school conducted research in the field of music education and musical pedagogy, studying the issues of integrating modern educational technologies into music lessons. In particular, scientific and practical developments have been created on the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in music lessons, improving the methodology of teaching national musical heritage, developing students' aesthetic thinking, and forming musical competencies. [4].

The scientific school of the professor also conducts scientific research on the effectiveness of using interactive methods in music education, the introduction of digital pedagogical elements into music lessons, and the integration of art and

pedagogy. These studies pay special attention to the development of students' creative independence, stage culture, musical thinking, and communicative competencies.

Today, the scientific and pedagogical school created by Professor Samikhon Ashirboyev serves as an important methodological basis for the modern education system. This scientific school:

- improving the quality of education;
- introducing innovative methods;
- training young scientists;
- developing pedagogical thinking;

it serves to improve the effectiveness of scientific research.

The scientific views of the professor are especially important in the development of the integration of pedagogy and philology. This makes it possible to train competent specialists to suit the needs of the modern educational system.

In conclusion, the scientific and pedagogical activity of the teacher plays an important role in the development of Uzbek pedagogy and philology. A solid scientific and Pedagogical School was formed as a result of the scientist's methodological views, innovative approaches and scientific leadership activities. The scientific school created by the professor is playing an important role in the development of pedagogical thought, training scientific personnel, improving the methodology of language teaching, and attracting young researchers to science. The scientific and pedagogical heritage of the teacher serves as an important methodological resource for future generations of researchers..

List of literature used:

1. Ashirboyev S. Uzbek Dialectology. – Tashkent: TDPU named after Nizami, 2013. – 87 p– Tashkent: Fan, 2021. – 410 b.

4. Karimov N. Scientific research methodology and principles of academic integrity. - Tashkent: Meridian, 2022. – 280 b.

5. Tursunova L. Methodology of teaching the native language as a second language. – Tashkent: University, 2022. – 310 p.

6. Yuldoshev, U. (2018). Problems of choosing methods and technologies in musical pedagogy. Eastern European Scientific Journal, 2022. – 310 p.

6. Yuldoshev, U. (2018). Problems of choosing methods and technologies in musical pedagogy. Eastern European Scientific Journal